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ANALYSIS OF THE ALGORITHM FOR THE FORMATION OF THE AMPLITUDE MODULATION LAW OF THE PROBING SIGNAL

INDIRA BAYZHUMANOVNA KOZHABAYEVA

senior teacher

Almaty University of Power Engineering and Telecommunications named after G. Daukeev,
Kazakhstan

Annotation. *The outcome of the subsequent processing stages, the formation of the amplitude law of modulation of the probing signal, directly depends on the quality of solving the problem of automatic detection. In addition, it significantly affects the tactical characteristics of the radar: the range of automatic target detection, the probability of false alarms, coordinate measurement errors, wiring coefficient, etc. All this determines the urgency of the task of developing new radio systems, as well as the modernization of those in service in our republic.*

Introduction

Modern radar facilities are multifunctional automated radar complexes with a wide range of tasks to be solved. The decision-making process of detecting the target signal in the radar is an integral part of the overall automated process of its operation. The outcome of the subsequent stages of radar information processing, coordinate measurement, recognition, and trajectory processing directly depends on the quality of solving the automatic detection problem. The operating condition of any equipment depends on the quality of the signal. To obtain a signal, there are many algorithms, one of which is the algorithm for forming the amplitude modulation law of the probing signal [1,2]

Keywords: *signal, modulation, radio, amplitude modulation of the signal, period, radio source, algorithm, bearing estimation.*

Recurrent M-sequences are pseudorandom binary sequences of maximum duration, which are generated by a linear generator on shift registers and have the maximum possible period:

$$N_D = 2^n - 1 \tag{1}$$

where n is the number of cascades of the linear generator. To obtain binary numbers, adders modulo 2 have been added to the linear generator. Figure 1.1 shows a block diagram of such a 98 generator for n = 10.

Figure 1.1 – Linear generator on shift registers for n = 10

The digital sequence at the output of the generator depends on both the feedback circuit and the initial loading (initialization) of the shift register. Figure 1.2 shows an example of the implementation of a linear sequence generator of maximum duration in the MathCad mathematical computing environment.

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d_M_1023(Nom_cod) :=
for k ∈ 0..9
  a_k ← 1
for i ∈ 0..1022
  d_M_i ← a_9
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_2 if Nom_cod = 1
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_7 ⊕ a_2 ⊕ a_1 if Nom_cod = 2
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_3 ⊕ a_2 ⊕ a_0 if Nom_cod = 3
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_7 ⊕ a_4 ⊕ a_0 if Nom_cod = 4
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_7 ⊕ a_4 ⊕ a_3 if Nom_cod = 5
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_8 ⊕ a_3 ⊕ a_0 if Nom_cod = 6
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_7 ⊕ a_3 ⊕ a_2 if Nom_cod = 7
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_4 ⊕ a_2 ⊕ a_1 if Nom_cod = 8
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_4 ⊕ a_1 ⊕ a_0 if Nom_cod = 9
  vx ← a_9 ⊕ a_8 ⊕ a_3 ⊕ a_1 if Nom_cod = 10
  for k ∈ 9,8..1
    a_k ← a_{k-1}
  a_0 ← vx
d_M
    
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Figure 1.2 - is an example of the implementation of a linear sequence generator of maximum duration in the MathCad environment

If we assume that the output binary sequence is removed from the last registers, and the initial contents of the registers consisted of only 99 units, then the modulation law of the rectangular CPM RI encoded by the 1023- element code of the M sequence will have the form shown in Figure 1.3

Figure 1.3 - is an example of an M-sequence consisting of 1023 elements

Possible requirements for the structure of the code is the approximation of the uncertainty body of such a law of modulation of the CFM radio pulse to a needle-shaped one with a complete absence of side lobes along the time axis [2,3] The cross section of the uncertainty body along the time axis represents a correlation function (Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4 - The correlation function of an M-sequence consisting of 1023 elements

Thus, it follows from Figure 1.4 that the maximum of the signal peaks according to the M-sequence law has a magnitude of the order $1/\sqrt{N_D}=0.031$ slowly decreasing with increasing number of discretized N_D . In addition, the use of a single code sequence generator for the probing signal will

simplify the implementation of the required impulse response corresponding to the current range to the target [3]

Calculate the required number of range channels to measure the range to the target. In accordance with Kotelnikov's theorem, the sampling step in time is $\Delta t_D = \frac{1}{2F_{max}}$. So for the specified parameters of radio relay communication $\Delta f_0 = 1/T_D = 3.03$ MHz, $\Delta t_d = 1/2F_{max} = 1/\Delta f_0 = 0,33$ мкс which corresponds to the range $\Delta r = 49,5$ m. Then, taking into account the maximum target detection range of $r_{max} = 5$ km, the number of range resolution elements that fit into the period of unambiguity will be:

$$N_r = 2 \cdot r_{max} / \Delta r_d \approx 122. \tag{2}$$

In this case, to simultaneously measure the range to the target, you will need to use $N_r = 122$ parallel range channels containing CF with different pulse characteristics [5] The algorithm for generating the impulse response for the j -th range channel ($N_r = 1, \dots$) It includes three stages:

- 1) Code sequence delay: $t_d = 2j\Delta r_d/c$
- 2) Multiplication of the original
- 3) Code sequence conversion

Figure 1.5 shows diagrams explaining the process of pulse characteristic formation

Figure 1.5 - Diagrams of the stages of formation of the impulse response of the matched filter j -th range channel

Thus, the considered algorithm makes it possible to form the impulse response of the SF the j th channel of the range, which corresponds to a mirror image of the code sequence of the probing signal.

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